

ON MONOCHROMATIC SOLUTIONS OF LINEAR EQUATIONS USING AT LEAST THREE COLORS

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Abstract

We study the number of monochromatic solutions to linear equations in $\{1, \dots, n\}$ when we color the set by at least three colors. We consider the r -commonness for $r \geq 3$ of linear equations with an odd number of terms and also prove that any 2-uncommon equation is r -uncommon over the integers for any $r \geq 3$.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and Motivation

In 1996, Graham, Rödl, and Ruciński [4] asked about the minimum number of monochromatic solutions to the Schur equation $x + y = z$ with $(x, y, z) \in [n]^3$, where the set $[n] := \{1, \dots, n\}$ is 2-colored. Robertson and Zeilberger [5] showed that the minimum number of monochromatic Schur triples in a 2-coloring of $[n]$ is asymptotically $n^2/11 + O(n)$. This is less than $(1/8 + o(1))n^2$, which is the expected number of monochromatic solutions under uniformly random 2-colorings.

One can ask a similar question for more general linear equations

$$a_1x_1 + \dots + a_kx_k = 0, \quad a_1, \dots, a_k \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 3}.$$

This problem has been studied for several linear equations, including generalized Schur triples, K -term arithmetic progressions, and constellations. In fact, it still remains unknown which linear equations have uniformly random 2-colorings that asymptotically minimize the number of monochromatic solutions.

We define a k -term linear equation to be *2-common over the integers* if any 2-coloring of $[n]$ has at least as many monochromatic solutions asymptotically (as $n \rightarrow \infty$) as uniformly random colorings. Otherwise, we say that the equation is *2-uncommon over the integers*. More generally, if we change 2 to any positive integer

r greater than 1, we can define linear equations to be r -common over the integers in a similar fashion.

Recently, Costello and Elvin [1] showed that all 3-term equations are 2-uncommon over the integers. In the same paper, they conjectured that an equation is 2-common over the integers if and only if the number of terms is even and the equation has a canceling partition. We say that the linear equation

$$a_1x_1 + \cdots + a_kx_k = 0 \tag{1}$$

has a *canceling partition* if we can partition the coefficients into pairs $\{a_i, a_j\}$ such that $a_i + a_j = 0$. Clearly, if a canceling partition exists, then k must be even.

More recently, Dong, Mani, Pham, and Tidor [2] showed that the conjecture is false by showing that the linear equation $x_1 + 2x_2 - x_3 - 2x_4 = 0$ is 2-uncommon over the integers. The case when the number of terms in Equation (1) is odd and at least five still remains unknown.

While commonness over the integers is still a mystery, Versteegen [8] proved that an equation is 2-uncommon over a finite abelian group G , with the order of G coprime to every coefficient of the equation if and only if k is even and the equation has no canceling partition. This generalizes the result of [3], where the same result over finite fields was proved. See also [6] for an introduction to the topic.

We also note that another motivation for considering r -commonness of a linear equation is because of the Sidorenko property of an equation, which was first introduced in [6]. The notion is inspired by Sidorenko’s conjecture on graphs [7], which is still a major open problem in extremal graph theory. We recall the definition here. Given a linear equation $L : a_1x_1 + \cdots + a_kx_k = 0$ over a finite abelian group G , if $\mathcal{C}(L)$ denotes the number of solutions of $L = 0$ in G^k , we say that L is *Sidorenko in* G if for every $A \subseteq G$ we have

$$t_L(1_A) \geq \left(\frac{|A|}{|G|}\right)^k$$

where 1_A is the indicator function of A and

$$t_L(1_A) := \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}(L)|} \sum_{v \in \mathcal{C}(L)} \prod_{i=1}^k 1_A(v_i).$$

Clearly, if an equation is Sidorenko over G , then it is r -common for every $r \geq 2$. The results for finite fields are given in [3], and for general finite abelian groups in [8]. One can think of the notion of r -commonness for $r \geq 3$ as being the case between Sidorenko and 2-common, which is often referred to simply as ‘common’ in the existing literature.

1.2. Main Results

We now explore the phenomenon of r -commonness for linear equations with $r \geq 3$. We first consider the r -commonness over the integers for k -term linear equations where $k > 1$ is an odd positive integer and $r > 2$. This problem is easier than in the case of 2-commonness. In fact, all such equations are r -uncommon over the integers as a corollary of the following theorem, whose proof will appear in Section 3.

Theorem 1. *Let G be an arbitrary nontrivial finite abelian group and let E be an arbitrary linear equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_{2m+1}x_{2m+1} = 0$ such that $a_i \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ for each $i = 1, \dots, 2m + 1$ with $m \geq 1$. Assume $|G|$ is coprime to each a_i for $i = 1, \dots, 2m + 1$. Then the equation E is r -uncommon over G for every $r \geq 3$.*

Corollary 1. *Let $m \geq 1$ be an integer and let E be a $(2m + 1)$ -linear equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_{2m+1}x_{2m+1} = 0$, where $a_i \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ for each $i = 1, \dots, 2m + 1$. Then E is r -uncommon over the integers for every $r \geq 3$.*

Next, we consider the case where the number of terms in the equation is even. As mentioned, it is known from [8] that every equation that has no canceling partition is 2-uncommon over an abelian group G , provided the order of G is coprime to every a_i . In particular, by Lemma 1, such an equation is 2-uncommon over the integers. As noted earlier, we have that the equation $x_1 + 2x_2 - x_3 - 2x_4 = 0$ is 2-uncommon over the integers. We have that these equations are also r -uncommon, using a different proof method than in Corollary 1, as shown in Section 3.

Theorem 2. *Let $k \geq 3$ and let E be a 2-uncommon equation over the integers $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_kx_k = 0$ with $a_i \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ for each $i = 1, \dots, k$. Then the equation is also r -uncommon over the integers for any $r \geq 3$.*

Corollary 2. *Every linear equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_{2m}x_{2m} = 0, m \geq 2$, that has no canceling partition is r -uncommon over the integers for any $r \geq 2$. The same is true for the equation $x + 2y - z - 2w = 0$.*

2. Notation and Conventions

We now introduce some notation that we will use throughout this paper. We write $f = O(g)$ or $f \ll g$ if there exists a constant C such that $|f| \leq Cg$. We denote a prime number by p , and a cyclic group of order ℓ is denoted by $\mathbb{Z}/\ell\mathbb{Z}$ where $\ell > 1$ is a positive integer. Let $f, g : G \rightarrow [0, 1]$, which we interpret as probabilistic colorings via

$$f(t) = \mathbb{P}[t \text{ is the first color}]$$

$$g(t) = \mathbb{P}[t \text{ is the second color}].$$

One may think that we use red, green, and blue as colors, with red being the first color, green the second color, and blue the third color. We define the *Fourier transform of f* , denoted by \hat{f} , by

$$\hat{f}(\xi) := \frac{1}{|G|} \sum_{t \in G} f(t) \mathbf{e}(-\xi \cdot t)$$

where $\mathbf{e}(x) = e^{2\pi i x}$ and ξ is a homomorphism from \widehat{G} to \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{Z} acting as $\xi : t \mapsto \xi \cdot t$. Here \widehat{G} denotes the dual group of G , which is isomorphic to G . The Fourier transform of g , denoted by \hat{g} , is defined similarly to \hat{f} .

We can write the expected number of red solutions of $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_{2m+1}x_{2m+1} = 0$ over G in terms of Fourier transforms:

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{number of red solutions}] = |G|^{2m} \sum_{t \in G} \hat{f}(a_1t) \dots \hat{f}(a_{2m+1}t).$$

Note that the formula above holds only if at least one of a_1, \dots, a_{2m+1} is coprime to $|G|$, which we always assume. The expected proportion of monochromatic solutions in G is given by

$$\begin{aligned} &\mu_{a_1x_1 + \dots + a_{2m+1}x_{2m+1} = 0}(f, g) \\ &= \sum_{t \in G} \hat{f}(a_1t) \dots \hat{f}(a_{2m+1}t) + \sum_{t \in G} \hat{g}(a_1t) \dots \hat{g}(a_{2m+1}t) \\ &\quad + \sum_{t \in G} (1 - \widehat{f - g})(a_1t) \dots (1 - \widehat{f - g})(a_{2m+1}t). \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

3. Linear Equations That Are r -Uncommon

We begin by proving Theorem 1. Corollary 1 follows from Theorem 1 and the following lemma, which appears as [1, Lemma 2.1]. For an arbitrary set S and an arbitrary linear equation $E : a_1x_1 + \dots + a_kx_k = 0$, we denote by $\mu(S)$ to be the proportion of the minimum number of monochromatic solutions relative to the total number of solutions of E in S^k .

Lemma 1. *Let E be a linear equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_{2m+1}x_{2m+1} = 0$. Then we have*

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu_E([n]) \leq \mu_E(\mathbb{Z}/\ell\mathbb{Z})$$

for any positive integer ℓ .

We now proceed to the proof of Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. Let E be a linear equation $a_1x_1 + \dots + a_{2m+1}x_{2m+1} = 0$ where $a_i \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$. We first prove that the equation is 3-uncommon and then show that it

is also r -uncommon for any $r > 3$ by generalizing the case where $r = 3$. We need to find f and g such that the quantity in (2) is less than $\frac{1}{3^{2m}}$. But we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mu_{a_1x_1+\dots+a_{2m+1}x_{2m+1}=0}(f, g) \\ &= \frac{1}{3^{2m}} + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{f}(a_1t) \dots \hat{f}(a_{2m+1}t) + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{g}(a_1t) \dots \hat{g}(a_{2m+1}t) \\ & \quad + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} (\widehat{1-f-g})(a_1t) \dots (\widehat{1-f-g})(a_{2m+1}t) \\ &= \frac{1}{3^{2m}} + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{f}(a_1t) \dots \hat{f}(a_{2m+1}t) + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{g}(a_1t) \dots \hat{g}(a_{2m+1}t) \\ & \quad + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} (-\hat{f}-\hat{g})(a_1t) \dots (-\hat{f}-\hat{g})(a_{2m+1}t). \end{aligned}$$

The last equality follows from the fact that for $s \neq 0$, we have $(\widehat{1-f})(s) = -\hat{f}(s)$. We refer to the quantity

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{f}(a_1t) \dots \hat{f}(a_{2m+1}t) + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{g}(a_1t) \dots \hat{g}(a_{2m+1}t) \\ & \quad + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} (-\hat{f}-\hat{g})(a_1t) \dots (-\hat{f}-\hat{g})(a_{2m+1}t) \end{aligned}$$

as the *deviation*.

We assume without loss of generality that $\hat{f}(0) = \hat{g}(0) = \frac{1}{3}$, which is equivalent to requiring that red, green, and blue appear with equal overall probability. To ensure that the proportion is less than that of a uniformly random coloring, it suffices to find f and g such that $\hat{f}(0) = \hat{g}(0) = \frac{1}{3}$ and the deviation is negative. Therefore, it is enough to find f and g such that $\hat{f}(0) = \hat{g}(0) = \frac{1}{3}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{f}(a_1t) \dots \hat{f}(a_{2m+1}t) + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} \hat{g}(a_1t) \dots \hat{g}(a_{2m+1}t) \\ & \quad + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} (-\hat{f}-\hat{g})(a_1t) \dots (-\hat{f}-\hat{g})(a_{2m+1}t) < 0. \end{aligned}$$

By Fourier inversion, f and g are uniquely determined by their Fourier coefficients. First, we note that f and g are real-valued if and only if \hat{f} and \hat{g} are Hermitian, i.e., $\overline{\hat{f}(s)} = \hat{f}(-s)$ and $\overline{\hat{g}(s)} = \hat{g}(-s)$. So we need to ensure this condition holds for \hat{f} and \hat{g} . Second, we need to make sure that the ranges of f and g are subsets of $[0, 1]$. To do this, we use the *Fourier inversion formula*

$$f(u) = \sum_{\xi \in \hat{G}} \hat{f}(\xi) \mathbf{e}(\xi \cdot u), u \in G$$

where we again use $\mathbf{e}(x) = e^{2\pi i x}$. By the triangle inequality, we have

$$|f(u) - 1/3| \leq \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} |\hat{f}(t)|. \tag{3}$$

By the same calculation, we also have

$$|g(u) - 1/3| \leq \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} |\hat{g}(t)|. \tag{4}$$

With these observations, we now construct f and g explicitly as follows.

We define f by setting

$$\hat{f}(s) = -\frac{2}{p^2}, \quad s \in G \setminus \{0\}$$

and g by setting

$$\hat{g}(s) = \frac{1}{p^2}, \quad s \in G \setminus \{0\}$$

We can take a prime p such that $p > |a_i|$ and $\gcd(a_i, p) = 1$ for each $i = 1, \dots, 2m+1$, with

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq \frac{1}{3} - \frac{2(p-1)}{p^2} &= \frac{1}{3} - \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} |\hat{f}(t)| \leq f(u) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2(p-1)}{p^2} = \frac{1}{3} + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} |\hat{f}(t)| \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq \frac{1}{3} - \frac{(p-1)}{p^2} &= \frac{1}{3} - \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} |\hat{g}(t)| \leq g(u) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{3} + \frac{(p-1)}{p^2} = \frac{1}{3} + \sum_{t \in G \setminus \{0\}} |\hat{g}(t)| \leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

for any $u \in G$. The above inequalities follow from Inequalities (3) and (4) and the specific values of \hat{f} and \hat{g} . These ensure that the images of f and g lie in $[0, 1]$. We also remark that \hat{f} and \hat{g} are Hermitian since \hat{f} and \hat{g} are real-valued and both take only one value except at zero.

We also require that $0 < f(u) + g(u) < 1$ for any $u \in G$, which can be guaranteed by taking p sufficiently large such that

$$0 < \frac{2}{3} - \frac{3(p-1)}{p^2} < \frac{2}{3} + \frac{3(p-1)}{p^2} < 1.$$

Recalling the Fourier coefficients of f and g again, we find that the deviation is

$$-\left(\frac{2}{p^2}\right)^{2m+1} + \left(\frac{1}{p^2}\right)^{2m+1} + \left(\frac{1}{p^2}\right)^{2m+1} < 0. \tag{5}$$

Therefore, every linear equation with $2m + 1$ terms is 3-uncommon.

To show that those equations are also r -uncommon for $r > 3$, we need to construct $r - 1$ functions f_1, \dots, f_{r-1} such that the deviation is negative. We generalize the construction used for the case $r = 3$. As in the case when $r = 3$, for $r > 3$ we require that $\hat{f}_j(0) = \frac{1}{r}$ for every $j \in \{1, \dots, r - 1\}$. Now we assign the values of their Fourier coefficients as follows. For $j = 1, 2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_1(s) &= -\frac{2}{p^2}, & s \in G \setminus \{0\}, \\ \hat{f}_2(s) &= \frac{1}{p^2}, & s \in G \setminus \{0\}. \end{aligned}$$

where p is a sufficiently large prime number in terms of a_1, \dots, a_{2m+1} , and also in terms of r so that $0 \leq f_j(u) \leq 1, u \in G, j = 1, 2$.

Then we define $\hat{f}_j(s) = 0$ for any $j = 3, \dots, r - 1$ and any $s \in G \setminus \{0\}$. Clearly, we have that each \hat{f}_j is Hermitian and $f_j(u) \in [0, 1]$ for any $u \in G$ and any $j = 1, \dots, r - 1$. By performing similar calculations to the case where $r = 3$, we also get that the deviation is negative, and we can choose p such that $0 < f_1(u) + \dots + f_{r-1}(u) < 1$ for any $u \in G$. This concludes the proof of Theorem 1. \square

Remark 1. We note that if we choose a sufficiently large p , although the deviation in (5) is negative, it becomes negligible and the quantity is much smaller compared to the size of the group G . It would be interesting to obtain such an r -uncommon coloring explicitly.

To prove Theorem 2, we use the probabilistic method instead of using the Fourier method.

Proof of Theorem 2. We claim that if an equation is $(r - 1)$ -uncommon over the integers, then it is also r -uncommon over the integers for any $r \geq 3$. This clearly implies the statement of the theorem.

Note that the total number of solutions with $x_i = x_j$ for some $i \neq j$ is $O(n^{k-1})$. Thus, for large n , such solutions are negligible. Thus, we can focus on solutions with pairwise distinct coordinates.

Now, let (x_1, \dots, x_k) be a solution of our linear equation in $[n]^k$ with $x_i \neq x_j$ for $i \neq j$, and let n be a sufficiently large integer such that the equation E is 2-uncommon over $[n]$. We consider an $(r - 1)$ -coloring of $[n]$ under which the equation is $(r - 1)$ -uncommon. We choose $\lfloor \frac{n}{r} \rfloor$ elements of $[n]$ uniformly at random, then we color those elements with the r -th color. Then if (x_1, \dots, x_k) is monochromatic

under the original coloring and $x_i \neq x_j$ for $i \neq j$, the probability that it will be monochromatic in the same color is

$$\left(\frac{r-1}{r}\right)^k.$$

If (x_1, \dots, x_k) is an arbitrary solution, it becomes monochromatic in the r -th color with probability

$$\left(\frac{1}{r}\right)^k.$$

Since the equation is $(r-1)$ -uncommon, the expected proportion of monochromatic solutions under r colors is less than

$$\left(\frac{r-1}{r}\right)^k \frac{1}{(r-1)^{k-1}} + \left(\frac{1}{r}\right)^k = \left(\frac{1}{r}\right)^{k-1}.$$

Hence, there is an r -coloring of $[n]$ such that the equation E is r -uncommon.

Since we started with an equation that is $(r-1)$ -uncommon, we get the result. \square

4. Open Problem

Costello and Elvin [1] used the Fourier method to show that equations of the form

$$x_1 + \dots + x_m = x_{m+1} + \dots + x_{2m} \tag{6}$$

are 2-common over the integers for any $m \geq 2$. While we proved that 2-uncommonness implies r -uncommonness for all $r \geq 3$, it is unknown whether 2-commonness implies r -commonness for $r \geq 3$. Even in the simplest case where $m = 2$ in (6), we are not yet able to determine whether it is 3-common or not.

This motivates the following question.

Question 1. Is there a linear equation that is r -uncommon for some $r \geq 3$ but s -common for some $s < r$?

We are particularly interested in equations with canceling partitions that are 2-common over the integers, since these remain poorly understood.

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